

Towards SIM: A Semantic Information Modeling Framework for Dataspaces Focused on Application Profiles

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Abstract.

Dataspaces enable sovereignty-preserving data sharing among organizations by supporting the ‘loose’ integration of heterogeneous data sources—structured, semi-structured, or unstructured—while keeping content data at the source. Their goal is seamless discovery and on-demand sharing of content data, governed by access and usage policies. Metadata is crucial for discovery, but the lack of established semantic modeling frameworks for domain-specific dataspace hinders interoperability.

To address this gap, we propose SIM, a semantic information modeling framework for domain-specific dataspace. It is a comprehensive framework that integrates building blocks such as ontologies, controlled vocabularies, application profiles (APs), and access and usage policies. While Semantic Web (SW) technologies promise interoperability, existing ontology development methodologies are insufficient for the application-specific data modeling needs of dataspace. SIM addresses this gap by promoting APs as flexible semantic data models (SDMs) that reuse existing SDMs, such as ontologies, and define context-specific constraints and recommendations.

In this paper, we focus on APs, and outline the foundational, governance, and operational aspects of their lifecycle management in dataspace, along with key future research directions. To support SIM’s goal of enabling effective collaboration between SW experts and domain experts, our proposal emphasizes the development and use of intuitive, low-code visual tools enhanced by GenAI to simplify and accelerate application profile development.

Keywords. semantic interoperability, application profiles, dataspace, ontologies

1. Introduction

Today, given the ever-increasing amount of data being generated, data management and sharing infrastructures are evolving rapidly [1,2,3,4]. Introduced in the mid-

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2000s [5], the concept of dataspace has evolved driven by the need for data sovereignty. It has transformed into an advanced form of multi-sided platforms [6] that enables B2B data sharing in a distributed, interoperable, sovereign, and trustworthy manner. Dataspace is a vital component of the European Data Strategy [7] and are being developed across various domains such as Culture, Health, Mobility, and Manufacturing [8].

Dataspace promotes data co-existence by allowing heterogeneous sources—semantic, structured, semi-structured, or unstructured—to be “loosely” integrated. To ensure simplicity, scalability, and sovereignty, content data remains at the source and is exchanged on demand in a peer-to-peer fashion. Dataspace participants are responsible for the model, format, and semantics of their *content data*. In contrast, for *metadata*, domain- and application-specific semantic data models (SDMs) or application profiles (APs) are developed collaboratively by SW experts and domain experts appointed by the dataspace governance body. These metadata APs are then prescribed to the dataspace participants. Unlike ontologies, APs enable application-specific knowledge representation and support enforcement of the closed-world assumption (CWA) [9]. However, no established framework currently exists for specifying, managing, and integrating the necessary SDMs, including such APs in dataspace.

To address this gap, we introduce SIM, a semantic information modeling framework for domain-specific dataspace. SIM consists of building blocks such as APs, ontologies, and controlled vocabularies for addressing their unique data modeling needs. SIM focuses on APs, their multifaceted modeling aspects, and recommends methodologies for enabling effective collaboration between SW experts and domain experts.

2. Related Work

Existing information modeling approaches in dataspace:

When establishing a new dataspace in a specific domain, multiple SDMs must be developed to represent metadata for various use cases, enabling the discovery of data sources that provide content data. Many dataspace initiatives typically create domain-specific information models (IMs) for this purpose. For instance, the Culture IM [10] from the Culture Dataspace project [11], DEMETER Agriculture IM [12] from the DEMETER project, the Green Deal IM [13,14] from the AD4GD project, the SEDI-MARK Marketplace IM [15] from the SEDIMARK project, and the DigiChecks IM [16] from the construction dataspace.

Dataspace development initiatives such as IDSA and Gaia-X provide core vocabularies, such as IDS IM [17] and Gaia-X schemas [18] but leave domain-specific IM development to individual initiatives [19,20]. The Data Spaces Blueprint v2 [21] published by the EU Data Spaces Support Centre DSSC outlines a high-level co-creation process but lacks a comprehensive IM framework. Without a standardized framework, initiatives create custom IMs, leading to redundancy and heterogeneity, and hindering cross-domain and cross-dataspace interoperability [22].

Existing ontology and application profile development methodologies:

The data modeling requirements of domain-specific dataspace are multi-faceted: (i) they need various types of SDMs such as ontologies, APs, and access and usage policies; (ii) while existing ontologies can be reused, they must develop APs tailored to specific use cases; (iii) they need to distinguish flexibly between metadata and content data; and finally, (iv) given the complexity of SW technologies [22,17,23], they must be ex-

pressed in a user-friendly manner. Therefore, existing ontology development methodologies, such as AMOD [24] or LOT [25], are only partially applicable.

Over the years, some frameworks and methodologies have been proposed for creating APs [26] such as the Singapore Framework [27] and Me4DCAP methodology [28] from the DCMI community. The more recent SEMIC Style Guide [29] offers guidance on creating Core Vocabularies and APs. However, there are currently no established methodologies specifically for developing APs tailored to dataspace. Therefore, there is a clear need for a comprehensive framework that addresses all information modeling aspects of domain-specific dataspace, along with a methodology for developing APs suited to these dataspace ecosystems.

3. Background: What are Application Profiles?

APs have been in tacit use for a long time [30]. In 1997, Lynch [31] defined APs as follows (paraphrased text in square brackets): “Profiles are *customizations of the [Z39.50] standard* for particular communities of implementers with common application requirements. [A profile can include agreements on using specific optional features, attribute sets, record syntaxes, and extended services, tailored to the community’s needs.]”

In the early 2000s, APs were prominently introduced by Heery and Patel [32] as “a type of metadata *schema* that consists of elements taken from one or more namespaces that are combined and optimized for a particular local application.” According to them, “an AP: (i) may draw elements from one or more existing namespaces [i.e., ontologies]; (ii) can not introduce new elements; (iii) may specify permitted schemes and values, [e.g., use of values only from a particular controlled vocabulary, or mandatory schemes such as use of particular formats for dates and personal names]; and (iv) can refine standard definitions, but it may only make it semantically narrower or more specific.”

In 2002, Baker, et al. [33] integrated the concept of APs with the then newly introduced Semantic Web [34]. According to them, an AP answers “what terms does your metadata use, and how does it use them”. It’s a common observation that while practitioners want to reuse standard ontologies, they often adapt them for specific application scenarios. APs provide a standard way to capture this specificity [32,33].

Over the years, the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) has further developed the concept of APs [35,36,37], defining them as [38]: “An AP is a metadata *design specification* that uses a selection of terms from multiple metadata vocabularies, with added constraints, to meet application-specific requirements.”

In 2023, SEMIC’s Style Guide for Semantic Engineers [29] reintroduced APs as follows: “An AP is a *data specification* aimed to facilitate the data exchange in a well-defined application context. It re-uses concepts from one or more semantic data specifications, while adding more specificity, by identifying mandatory, recommended, and optional elements, addressing particular application needs, and providing recommendations for controlled vocabularies to be used. Formally, the AP encompasses (a) reused ontology specifications (one or many) and (b) its own data shape specification. Optionally it may include (c) reused data shape specifications (one or many), and (d) it may provide its own ontology specification to fill the ontological gaps.”

The W3C Data Exchange Working Group (DXWG), in the 2024 W3C Editor’s Draft “Profile Guidance” [39], defines APs as “A *named set of constraints* on one or more identified base specifications, including the identification of any implementing subclasses of datatypes, semantic interpretations, vocabularies, options and parameters of those base

Figure 1. The concept and building blocks of SIM, a semantic information modeling framework for dataspace. Legend: colored boxes indicate aspects addressed in this paper; bb stands for building block, t stands for type, f stands for follows.

specifications necessary to accomplish a particular function.” In 2025, the Data Spaces Blueprint [21], a de facto standard for dataspace, defined an AP as follows: “An AP is a *data model* for applications that fulfill a particular use case. In addition to shared semantics, it also allows additional restrictions to be imposed, such as recording cardinalities or the use of certain code lists. An AP can serve as documentation for analysts and developers.”

DCAT-AP [40], an AP for data catalogs in Europe is a widely-known example that extends the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) [41] with refined definitions, usage notes, constraints (e.g., property cardinalities, commitment levels: mandatory, recommended, optional), and controlled vocabularies. It also incorporates classes and properties from other ontologies where necessary. Scrocca et al. [23] note that domain-specific extensions like GeoDCAT-AP for spatial data and StatDCAT-AP for statistical datasets adapt DCAT-AP by: (i) extending controlled vocabularies for values, (ii) defining additional metadata properties (e.g., for quality process, legal access details), and (iii) adjusting cardinalities and obligations for metadata properties. In domain-specific dataspace, mobilityDCAT-AP [23] is an example of a domain-specific extension of DCAT-AP which is referred to as a formal *metadata specification* for mobility data portals.

Thus, while some initiatives define APs as customizations of standards, others as a schema, design/data/metadata specification, data model, or set of constraints, they are consistent with each other on a broader conceptual level. In contrast to SEMIC’s AP definition, while acknowledging that an “own” ontology is often needed, SIM completely separates the aspects of APs and ontologies. Furthermore, like SEMIC, SIM also insists on having a human-readable component to APs, as further detailed in Section 5. SIM, aligned with the DSSC Blueprint, refers to APs as a specific type of SDMs.

4. SIM Building Blocks

Semantic data modeling in dataspace must address three layers: data, dataspace, and domain [42]. SIM targets the domain layer, serving as a reusable resource for domain-specific dataspace initiatives [8]. SIM’s building blocks (Figure 1) are as follows: **Application profiles:** Dataspace need various types of APs: Dataspace-specific, domain-specific, and access and usage policy templates. SIM focuses on domain-specific APs. Given the unique dataspace requirement to distinguish between metadata and content data, and with the governance body creating and prescribing only metadata models, APs are further divided into common Metadata APs for discovery and community-driven Content Data APs. Each type can be organized for reuse and minimal interoperability guarantees across specific application scenarios as:

General & Specific APs (GAPs & SAPs): For many dataspace, it might be beneficial to first create a common GAP for a general use case and then derive SAPs for concrete use case scenarios. GAPs can be convention-based, selecting a subset of elements from existing ontologies, and imposing only minimal restrictions (constraints, cardinalities, commitments/obligations) that are foreseen to be applicable to all derived SAPs.

Ontologies: Existing ontologies and vocabularies are reused as much as possible. However, it is often the case that existing concepts have to be extended or new concepts have to be defined. This is done in the form of one or more new ontologies.

Controlled vocabularies: Controlled vocabularies, authority tables, or code lists are used as enumerations for standardized values while instantiating APs.

Technical and governance best practices: Best practices should be identified and followed for the lifecycle management of SIM building block artifacts to ensure comprehensive, consistent, and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) [43] instances. Such practices for APs are discussed in Section 5.

5. Application Profiles in Domain-specific Dataspace: Foundations, Technologies, Best Practices, and Future Directions

Although APs were introduced over two decades ago, they remain under-researched [9]. This section explores the foundational, organizational, and operational aspects and best practices for their lifecycle management in dataspace, as illustrated in Figure 2.

5.1. Fundamental Aspects

Meta-model, conceptual model & language for APs: Heery and Patel [32], Baker et al. [33], and the SEMIC Style Guide [29] advocate for RDF as a metamodel for APs. The Data Specification Vocabulary (DSV) [44,45] provides RDF/OWL classes and properties to formally represent APs. For constraint representation, candidate languages include SHACL [46] and ShEx [47], which can also be used to validate RDF graphs. A conceptual model for APs must address questions such as: Can APs extend other APs? Can ontologies extend APs? And can APs themselves be modeled as ontologies?

Enforcing CWA using APs: SW technologies, such as OWL-based ontologies, typically operate under the open-world assumption (OWA), which means that if something is not known or specified, it cannot be assumed to be false. This leads to challenges like undecidability and incomplete inferences in real-world dataspace. To ensure strict metadata validation and reliable behavior, dataspace must reconcile OWA with the CWA, achievable through APs. A hybrid approach combining OWA for extensible semantics with CWA for validation is crucial for interoperability and discovery in dataspace.

Interpreting APs: Monotonic vs non-monotonic reasoning: Monotonic reasoning keeps conclusions unchanged despite new information, while non-monotonic logic allows conclusions to evolve with new data. In dataspace, where information can be incomplete or delayed, it's essential to determine which reasoning type to use and when.

Potential issues with using APs: Allowing APs to extend other APs may cause semantic drift [33]. Despite this, APs explicitly document practical adaptations of standards, enabling consistency assessment; and semantic drift is anyway inevitable [33].

5.2. Governance and Operational Aspects and Best Practices

Methodologies for AP development & lifecycle management: We are developing the *AP-first* methodology [48] for domain-specific dataspace, based on requirements out-

Figure 2. Aspects concerning lifecycle management of application profiles in domain-specific dataspace.

lined in Section 2 and insights from the German Culture Dataspace project [11]. AP-first is agile, iterative, user-friendly, and application-focused, emphasizing effective collaboration between SW experts and domain experts to prioritize AP creation.

Platforms for collaborative development, version control & publication of artifacts:

Prominent vocabularies such as DCAT and Schema.org use GitHub for version control, and collaboration. Best practices for structuring Git repositories to manage SIM artifacts need to be explored. For publishing AP artifacts, existing ontology publication practices and tools such as WIDOCO [49], ReSpec [50], and FOOPS! [51] need to be examined.

Validation & evaluation: It needs to be examined whether existing ontology evaluation approaches and tools, such as OOPS! [52], are applicable to APs. Initial results indicate that competency questions-based evaluation is highly effective for evaluating APs [10].

Versioning, release management & data contracts: An AP must be versioned and released to ensure users do not experience disruptions from version upgrades, respecting data contracts. Users should detect breaking changes and smoothly transition their data instances to new versions. Semantic Versioning 2.0.0 [53] can be used for this purpose.

Documentation contents & publication guidelines: AP documentation must include competency questions, provenance details, example data instances, queries, and metadata such as licensing and maintainer information to facilitate adoption. Furthermore, existing publication best practices such as FAIR principles [43], use of persistent identifiers such as w3id or PURL, W3C Best Practices for Publishing Linked Data (2014) [54], Best Practice Recipes for Publishing RDF Vocabularies (2008) [55], and Linked Data principles [56] should be followed.

5.3. Tooling and Representations

User-friendly visual modeling formats & single source of truth (SSoT): There is growing need for intuitive visual representations of SDMs that are both human- and machine-readable [57,29,22]. UML class diagram-like models simplify complex SDMs, as seen in DCAT and DCAT-AP documentations. A practical need is adapting version control to highlight the “diff” of changes in visual models. To streamline SIM building block development, an SSoT-based approach can be employed to generate multiple artifacts from a single structure. LinkML [58] supports this by converting a YAML schema into OWL, SHACL, PlantUML, and documentation, reducing effort and technical barriers. The SEMIC Style Guide [29,59] recommends UML as a preferred SSoT.

Low-code visual interfaces & GenAI to ensure user-friendliness: Collaborative low-code tools like draw.io enhance usability and inclusivity, with LOT (Chowlk [60]) and SEMIC promoting UML diagrams for modeling. However, current tools lack dynamic,

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bi-directional translation between visual and formal representations. Future tools should support AP development, formalization, and visualization (e.g., Dataspecer [45]), and browsing class/property hierarchies, like Schema.org. Low-code query interfaces are needed for non-experts to discover data sources. Meanwhile, developing SDMs involves complex tasks that can burden SW experts and limit domain expert participation. GenAI can offer potential solutions [22], including chat interfaces for AP visualization and editing, acting as a pair designer and recommending reusable resources, such as ontologies.

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